

TECHNOLOGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENVIRONMENTAL COMPETENCE IN FUTURE TEACHERS IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM OF DEVELOPED COUNTRIES

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Abstract. *This article covers environmental initiatives in the education system of different countries, the main content of programs and ways to integrate environmental education in the higher education system. Countries are evaluated and sorted by their environmental indicators, which allows us to determine the current situation in connection with the main environmental problems and initiatives in the field of Education.*

Keywords: *environmental education, competency-based approach, environmental competencies, environmental personality, teacher professional training, upbringing, environmental education, environmental practice, ecosystem, thrift, nature, land and underground resources, water resources, fauna, strategy, environmental situation, method, thinking, competence.*

In order to make responsible decisions in modern complex environmental conditions, it is important that a person has in-depth knowledge not only in different areas of the environment, but also has the ability to act in a particular or crisis environmental situation. Being environmentally friendly is to act skillfully in a particular environmental situation based on the knowledge and experience gained previously. Environmental compensation is a set of environmental preservation of interrelated personal qualities (knowledge, skills, qualifications, methods of activity) necessary for future teachers. Environmental compensation is the ability, readiness and experience of a person to preserve the environment, solve environmental problems. Environmental compensation is the ability to use theoretical knowledge, practical skills and skills acquired in the field of Environmental Science in practice, using them in solving practical and theoretical issues encountered in everyday life. Environmental competency Latin: means *competens*–Worthy, has the ability

In particular, the concept of the development of environmental education in 2017-2021, the unconditional implementation of the tasks set out in the strategy of action on the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, contributing to the solution of environmental problems on the territory of the Republic with the introduction of an educational system, increasing the environmental literacy of the growing younger generation, , it is important in that it is aimed at the effective organization of the process of environmental education and education [2]. One of the main areas of modern education is the greening of all areas of the educational process, the implementation of which is possible in conditions of continuous environmental education and enlightenment. The development of environmental competence in future teachers, taking into account the arrival of young teachers in schools every year, is one of the factors for the modernization of the entire educational system.

It is also considered one of the most important tasks before us to solve environmental problems, to develop a solution for it. At the same time, the head of state Shavkat Mirziyoyev, on July 12, 2017, at a video session with representatives of the Houses of the Supreme Assembly, political parties and the environmental movement of Uzbekistan, stated that “the most important issue is the need to seriously raise the environmental culture of the population.”[1]

Throughout the entire history of mankind, the attitude of society to nature has been deeply opposed: humanity, on the one hand, appeared in the process of the evolution of the Earth and is an integral part of the nature of the Earth, on the other hand, man. The use of natural resources to meet one's needs is what separates oneself from the environment.

One of the urgent tasks is the reform of the higher pedagogical education system in our country, the provision of qualified personnel, the radical improvement of the quality of training of competitive specialists based on the adaptation of national, professional requirements to international templates. Therefore, in accordance with the new requirements of Science and technology and production, the need arises to develop environmental competence as an important aspect of professional competence of future teachers. Environmental education is not an invention of our time. The goal of any education is to best prepare the younger generation to interact with the natural and social environment. Modern environmental education differs from environmental education in previous years in that it occurs in the context of a global environmental crisis and must respond to the complexity of the environmental problems facing humanity.

Decided to create an international program for education in the field of Ecology.

International policy in the field of environmental education implies the continuity of a person from an early age throughout his life: Greening the content of all subjects taught in educational institutions, closely linking ecology with economics. The content of environmental education and the methods of its implementation should have their own characteristics at the global, national-regional and local level.[7]

In Russia, in the period up to 2030, the foundations of state policy in the field of environmental development for the development of environmental education and education, the formation of ecological culture were developed. Within the framework of environmental education, the process of forming an environmental competence of an individual takes on a socio-cultural orientation, develops on the basis of the environmental consciousness of the individual, which becomes the main regulatory component of the relationship between man and nature.

The ecological system has been the most stable system for many centuries, including all flora and fauna, marine and terrestrial zones. However, in the modern world, human civilization and globalization are the main culprits of the constant change in the environment. According to the 2018 Environmental Performance Index, Human Behavior has had devastating consequences, including: climate change, global warming, water scarcity, drought, deforestation, flooding, and air pollution.[5]

Due to the above-mentioned environmental problems, our planet is facing a serious environmental crisis. The current environmental situation leads to disasters and tragedies, which make us think about the present and future of the planet. This necessitates immediate action to address global problems, primarily by environmental education of the population, including the introduction of its components into the school education system.

N.M. According to Ardoin, well-developed environmental education programs for the future generation have the potential not only to study the environment, human-ecosystem relations,

science and other sciences, but also to strengthen environmental and social ties, including achieving the desired results. Skills, motivation, interest and inspiration are needed.[6] Expanding the boundaries of the specific current topic of any program, we can see a wide range of possibilities in which environmental education can really achieve more, which has been shown in dozens of empirical studies (I.D.Zvereva, N.A.Rykova, B.G.Iogannsen, A.P.Sidelkovsky, et al.). The authors draw conclusions about key features that must be included in environmental education programs to encourage and empower students to influence environmental change.

Teachers have put a great deal of effort into developing environmental education programs that cover students' knowledge and competencies in environmental issues. The authors examine the effectiveness of such programs in terms of both student educational outcomes and the intergenerational impact that occurs when children discuss their educational experiences with their parents and other family members.[1]

M.J.Stern, R.B.Powell and D.Recent reviews of environmental education programs for schoolchildren by scientists such as Hill show that such programs can give a wide range of positive results for participants, including: increased knowledge; more positive attitude towards the environment and behavioral intentions; increased self-confidence and social interaction; and, among other things, improve academic motivation and performance. S.B. other applications developed by. Nielsen and D.E.Hunter focuses on building a student's emotional connection with wildlife, allowing them to become ecologically active.[7]

Today, ecology is a kind of tool for the preservation and development of Man and the continuation of human organization.[3]

The increasing role of the family in the modern Western educational model is one of the leading trends in the development of European environmental pedagogy. Various associations – family education groups, parent associations, women's associations, socio-cultural animation institutions structure their work in such a way that, from preschool age, the environment has a beneficial effect on the development of the child. For example, the Mannerheim Child Protection League in Finland brings together parents, doctors and teachers. She cares about changing the urban environment, taking into account the interests of children. The work of the league departments is so effective that local authorities are constantly forced to take into account the interests of children in environmental protection policies. If necessary, the league organizes environmental protection activities, shapes public opinion, and thus affects the government.[4]

In turn, environmental competence in future teachers is the necessary level of its preparation, including the values and meanings of environmental (environmental-pedagogical) activities, basic environmental knowledge, as well as experience in solving socially significant environmental problems. Practical are considered problems based on environmental activities. Environmental competence of an individual is formed on the basis of basic competencies. Glazachev, the main system of environmental competencies of the future teacher's personality, which reveals important aspects of the concept of "ecological culture of personality", is presented as follows: - has the ability to respond responsibly to the natural environment based on the recognition of its universal value; - understands the essence of the natural boundaries of modern socio-economic development and the reasons for the environmental crisis;

- can assess the results and consequences of its activities in terms of environmental compliance (biosphere compliance), non-harm to nature or minimization;

- has activity and behavioral skills suitable for nature; – is able to emotionally and emotionally perceive the risk of destruction of the natural environment, showing the will to protect and protect it;

-there is a need for activities in the field of Ecology and environmental management;

- has a sense of nature, can perceive its greatness and beauty; - has the need to communicate with nature, be in natural landscapes;

- has a holistic worldview and attitude [8].

Direct communication with nature plays an important role in the formation of Student Environmental competence, since a teacher of any profile can organize the following events:

- promoting conservation ideas among students and adults;

- maintaining the cleanliness of the school area;

-involvement of parents, representatives of local public authorities, reserves, museums, libraries, public organizations, etc.in environmental activities.[4]

The requirements of such an ideology are more difficult than the tasks of protecting the environment and reducing the flow of pollution. A new system of environmental knowledge should help current and future professionals organize human activities in the context of increasing environmental restrictions to prevent the emergence of environmental disasters. In order to achieve these goals, that is, in the training of highly qualified pedagogical personnel, it is necessary to activate all the possibilities of environmental competence, direct its entire system of values to radical, humanism, fully reveal the importance of nature that does not pass for Man. In providing environmental education to students, we will be able to jointly explain the relationship between nature and society on a scientific basis, training future teachers will require us to improve the system in our knowledge of the future generation about the analysis of environmental problems.

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